

Multilingual signage and the making of Pattaya's urban linguistic landscape

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This study explores the multilingual signage landscape of Pattaya, a major international tourist hub in Thailand. Using photographic evidence, field observations, and interviews with government officials and business owners, it analyzes the types, distribution, and linguistic composition of signs in key commercial areas. The findings show that Thai dominates in peripheral and residential zones, while English is the most common foreign language, followed by Chinese, Russian, and others. Signage patterns vary by location and business type, reflecting tourist demographics and spatial clustering. Multilingualism is most visible in central and beachfront areas, where signage serves both communicative and symbolic functions. The study challenges the conventional top-down and bottom-up divide by emphasizing decentralized, business-led language practices. It concludes with recommendations for local policymakers and urban planners to foster inclusive and culturally aware signage in a rapidly globalizing urban environment.

Keywords: Linguistic Stratification; Multilingual Signage; Pattaya City; Urban Linguistic Landscape

1. Introduction

The tourism sector in Thailand has expanded significantly in the past decade, with international arrivals increasing steadily from 2012 to 2019 and exceeding 39 million visitors annually (Ministry of Tourism and Sports, n.d.). As a result, tourism now plays a pivotal role in the country's economic development. According to the World Tourism Organization, Thailand ranks fourth globally in tourism revenue (TAT Review Magazine, 2019), with major cities and coastal provinces drawing sustained interest from international travelers. This rapid growth has transformed not only Thailand's economy but also its linguistic landscape. In tourist hubs, the presence of diverse languages is now an everyday reality—particularly in public signage, business advertising, and service interactions. In response, provincial governments have introduced

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tourism development strategies aimed at improving communication and access for international visitors. Cities across Thailand's regions have seen an increase in foreign languages in the public domain, reflecting broader patterns of globalization, cultural mixing, and commercial multilingualism.

In this context, Pattaya, a major coastal city in Chonburi Province, offers a compelling case for investigation. Located close to Suvarnabhumi International Airport and known for its beach attractions and vibrant nightlife, Pattaya has become one of Thailand's most visited destinations. The city's infrastructure, business activity, and population have become increasingly international, with visible signs of linguistic diversity. Preliminary observations show that signage across the city incorporates English, Chinese, Russian, Arabic, and other languages, reflecting both demographic trends and targeted commercial communication. Despite this visible multilingualism, there is a lack of systematic research on how language is selected, presented, and functionally distributed in Pattaya's signage. Prior studies—e.g., Sari et al. (2024)—have examined linguistic landscapes in capital cities or institutional contexts, but few have investigated tourism-driven multilingualism in secondary global cities like Pattaya, where informal language planning and commercial decision-making drive language use more than formal policy. Moreover, it remains unclear how signage practices differ across sectors and spatial zones, and how these practices reflect issues such as linguistic hierarchy, commodification, or symbolic exclusion.

This study addresses this gap by analyzing Pattaya's multilingual signage across various tourism-related sectors and city zones. It investigates (1) the types of languages used, (2) the patterns of bilingual and multilingual combinations, and (3) the differences between public (top-down) and private (bottom-up) signage practices (cf. Ben-Rafael et al., 2006). The study also considers how language use in signage reflects broader sociolinguistic dynamics such as tourism flows, business targeting, and the symbolic positioning of Thai versus foreign languages. As such, the study aims to examine how multilingual signage in Pattaya reflects patterns of linguistic hierarchy, commercial intent, and sociolinguistic diversity in a tourism-driven urban context. The objectives are as follows:

- To identify the language choices, combinations, and visibility patterns used in public and commercial signage across Pattaya.
- To explore how multilingual signage varies across business sectors and geographic zones, and what these reveal about tourism-driven multilingualism and symbolic inclusion or exclusion.

- To compare signage practices in the public (top-down) and private (bottom-up) sectors to understand how different actors shape the city's linguistic landscape.

2. Background

As King and Carson (2016) observe, cities are linguistically dynamic spaces where written and spoken language circulate rapidly. Multilingualism in such spaces often emerges not only from demographic diversity but also from deliberate language choices driven by tourism, branding, and market logic. Franceschini (2011) defines multilingualism as a core human competence shaped by social and economic contexts, while Maher (2017) views it as a communicative practice reflecting the realities of mobility, migration, and globalization. Language, in this context, becomes both a tool and a symbol—used not only to communicate but also to construct identity and attract economic opportunity.

In the tourism sector, language is inseparable from service delivery. As Nomnian et al. (2020) point out, the use of multiple languages is an essential feature of tourism spaces, where communication must accommodate both domestic and international visitors. This has contributed to the development of multilingual public signage, which provides a tangible representation of how languages coexist and compete in the public sphere. This phenomenon is commonly analyzed through the framework of Linguistic Landscape (LL) research, which examines (1) how languages appear in public signage, (2) what functions they serve, and (3) how they reflect power relations, social inclusion, or exclusion.

Landry and Bourhis (1997) originally defined linguistic landscape as the visibility and salience of languages on public and commercial signage—ranging from street signs and advertisements to government notices and institutional boards. Later scholars expanded this scope. Ben-Rafael et al. (2006) introduced a distinction between top-down signage (produced by government bodies and public institutions) and bottom-up signage (produced by private businesses and individuals). Shohamy (2015) further emphasized that all signs, whether official or informal—serve as sites where ideologies, identities, and economic motives intersect. Together, these frameworks provide a foundation for analyzing how multilingual signage emerges in different sectors and how it reflects underlying sociolinguistic forces.

Likewise, Sari et al. (2024) noticed that “factors shaping [shop] names include linguistic, commercial, and cultural aspects, with foreign influences recognized for their appeal” and that “opinions on their prestige vary.” They argued that “[shop] owners strategically choose names to attract customers, match their products, convey luxury, and display the local culture. They concluded their

study by suggesting that “it is necessary to balance English dominance [in shop signage] to preserve local identity.”

In this connection, the current study adopts a qualitative research design to investigate multilingual signage practices in Pattaya, Thailand, with a focus on public and private sector contexts.

3. Method

Data collection included photographic documentation, stakeholder interviews, and field observation to explore the relationship between language use, tourism development, and commercial activity.

3.1. Data

A total of 1,814 signs were initially photographed from ten purposively selected streets in Pattaya. These streets were chosen based on their proximity to the coastline and their popularity among domestic and international tourists. From the full dataset, a subset of 903 signs was selected for analysis using the following criteria: (1) clearly legible text, (2) prominent placement in the public space, (3) minimal physical deterioration, and (4) permanence. This selective sampling ensured analytical consistency and focused on signs that are both publicly visible and representative of Pattaya’s commercial and tourism infrastructure.

The selected signs were categorized into seven tourism-related business types, based on patterns observed during fieldwork and adapted from Sarot and Kraissame (2019). The categories are as follows: pubs, bars, and restaurants; accommodations; money exchange services; pharmacies; healthcare services; Thai massage and spas; and miscellaneous businesses. Multiple businesses of the same type—regardless of ownership—were grouped under a single category to reflect dominant economic functions rather than proprietorship. The classification was refined through on-site observation to reflect local economic realities and signage variation.

To complement the signage data, semi-structured interviews were conducted with representatives from six government agencies directly involved in tourism management, city planning, and language policy at the local level. Purposive sampling was used to select participants whose roles were relevant to the study’s objectives. Each interview was conducted at a time and location convenient for the participants, ensuring minimal disruption to their work. Prior to recording, informed consent was obtained to address ethical considerations and privacy concerns. Notes and audio recordings were taken to ensure accuracy.

In addition, unstructured interviews were conducted with private-sector vendors—including (1) shop owners and (2) signage providers—to gather supplementary insights into the decision-making processes behind language selection and signage design. These interviews offered valuable context to understand how business owners respond to tourist demographics and regulatory frameworks. All interview protocols, including consent forms and interview questions, were reviewed and approved by the institutional Research Ethics Committee before data collection began.

3.2. Procedure

The signage data were analyzed descriptively using frequency and percentage calculations to identify dominant languages, language combinations, and patterns of multilingualism across business types. Signs were also examined for their structure (e.g., language order, script type, visual prominence) to support thematic interpretation.

Interview transcripts were subjected to content analysis, through which recurring themes were identified and categorized according to their relevance to language use, tourism dynamics, and signage practices. Non-essential information was excluded to maintain analytical focus.

Field observations were also integrated to enrich the data and provide contextual insight into the spatial distribution of signs and business activities. Pattaya's tourism development plans were examined through stakeholder interviews and compared against observed signage trends to assess alignment or disparity between policy and practice.

4. Results

This study investigated 903 multilingual signs collected from various public and private locations in Pattaya, supported by interviews with government officials, business owners, and signage vendors. The findings reflect Pattaya's transformation into a highly multilingual urban space shaped by international tourism, commercial interests, and informal language practices.

Overall, the analysis confirms that Thai remains the foundational language in the city's signage landscape, reflecting its legal and symbolic status as the national language. It appears on most signs, either alone or alongside foreign languages, and is widely used for compliance with municipal regulations and signage tax requirements. However, its presence is often symbolic rather than communicative—especially in tourist zones, where Thai text may appear in smaller font sizes or peripheral positions. By contrast, English emerges as the dominant language in signage across nearly all business types. It functions as

the city's de facto 'lingua franca' (cf. Salmani Nodoushan, 2024), used to communicate with a broad spectrum of international tourists and expatriates.

In many cases, English replaces or visually overtakes Thai in signage, especially in sectors such as hospitality, dining, and nightlife. Its prominence reflects not only its global prestige but also its perceived commercial utility in reaching foreign customers. Other foreign languages—including Chinese, Russian, Arabic, and Korean—also appear frequently but in more targeted ways. Their use corresponds to specific tourist demographics and is typically limited to particular zones or business types. For instance, Chinese is prevalent in signage for restaurants, retail stores, and massage parlors catering to Chinese tour groups, while Russian and Arabic are commonly found in nightlife districts and halal eateries, respectively. These languages often appear as additional layers, either as window decals or add-on panels, signaling their supplementary role in reaching niche markets.

Business owners consistently expressed a pragmatic orientation toward language choice, selecting languages based on perceived customer needs, tourist trends, and signage costs. Interviews revealed that many owners do not seek to be fully inclusive linguistically, but instead focus on displaying just enough language to attract and inform their primary customer base. Signage is treated less as a site of cultural expression and more as a commercial tool. This finding reflects the concept of language commodification, where linguistic choices are governed by their potential to generate economic value.

The data also point to the increasing visual multilingualism of Pattaya, even in the absence of a formal multilingual policy. While there is no explicit directive mandating foreign language use on signs, both public and private actors respond to the realities of a global tourist economy. Interviews with municipal officers suggest an implicit understanding of the role that multilingual signage plays in improving the city's accessibility and international image. For example, English is selectively added to public signs near tourist attractions, police stations, and hospitals, while private businesses adopt other languages according to commercial interest.

Although not all signage in Pattaya is multilingual, the cumulative presence of multiple scripts and languages throughout the city creates a landscape in which multilingualism is normalized and increasingly expected. In some areas, signs in four or more languages are common, particularly in high-traffic tourism zones. Elsewhere, signage may alternate between bilingual (Thai–English) and monolingual formats depending on the area's commercial focus and clientele. In sum, the findings reveal a layered and strategic approach to language use in signage, shaped by a combination of national policy, tourism economics, and local agency. Thai provides symbolic grounding and legal compliance, English serves as the commercial and international default, and additional languages

are incorporated to attract specific customer segments. Signage is thus a site where language hierarchies are visually constructed and where commercial decisions intersect with sociolinguistic realities.

To interpret these findings more systematically, the results are presented across four thematic areas that reflect the core dynamics observed in the data: (1) language strategies by business type, (2) linguistic hierarchy, visibility, and layout, (3) top-down vs. bottom-up signage practices, and (4) geographic patterns and tourist demographics

4.1. Language strategies by business type

This section explores how language is employed across different tourism-related business categories in Pattaya, based on signage observed on ten prominent streets. Following Backhaus's (2006) typology, signs were classified as monolingual (one language), bilingual (two languages), or multilingual (three or more languages). The classification was applied across seven major business sectors: (1) pharmacies, (2) healthcare services, (3) money exchanges, (4) Thai massage and spas, (5) accommodations, (6) pubs, bars, and restaurants, and (7) miscellaneous businesses.

The signage data, summarized in Appendix A., reveal a strategic deployment of languages aligned with the commercial goals and clientele of each business type. A total of ten languages were documented, including Thai, English, Chinese, Korean, Russian, Arabic, German, Hindi, Japanese, and Vietnamese. Language distribution varied significantly by business type and sign format.

Table 1
Percentage Distribution of Each Sign Type

Type	Monolingual	Bilingual	Multilingual
pharmacy	7%	4%	35%
healthcare services	8%	7%	1%
money exchanges	4%	2%	8%
Thai massage and spas	6%	5%	7%
accommodations	11%	39%	3%
pubs, bars, and restaurants	40%	28%	32%
miscellaneous businesses	24%	15%	15%

Table 1 reports the percentages of monolingual, bilingual, and multilingual signage across business categories. The analysis reveals distinct patterns in how language is mobilized to reach local and international audiences. Across all sectors combined, monolingual signs account for 36%, bilingual signs for 34%, and multilingual signs for 30% of the total sample. This relatively balanced distribution suggests that businesses in Pattaya employ diverse

signage strategies depending on sector-specific needs and customer demographics. However, variation by business type is substantial.

Monolingual signs directed messaging in hospitality venues which are most frequently found in the pub, bar, and restaurant category, accounting for 40% of signage in this sector. These signs typically featured Thai, English, or Chinese. Business owners in this category reported a preference for simplicity, using a single dominant language to attract specific tourist demographics. For instance, a kebab shop on South Pattaya Road uses English exclusively on its storefront signage, while displaying menus in Russian and Arabic. The absence of Thai was explained by the owner's belief that Thai patrons could interpret English with ease, thereby prioritizing efficiency and clarity for foreign clientele (see Figure 1).

Figure 1.

Kebab Shop (Turkish Food) on South Pattaya Road (Source: Sarot, 2022)

Bilingual signage is most prominent in accommodation businesses (39%), reflecting international service standards and a need to accommodate both Thai and foreign guests. Thai–English combinations prevail in this group, with Thai fulfilling national regulatory expectations and English supporting international hospitality norms. By way of contrast, multilingual signage is especially frequent in pharmacies (35%), where the inclusion of multiple foreign languages supports clarity in essential health communication. The need to assist a wide range of customers—from tourists to long-term expatriates—drives pharmacies to display signs in combinations such as Thai–English–Chinese, and even four or five languages. Larger hotels, where bilingual signage dominates, often display English in larger font or more central placement than

Thai, reflecting the influence of global branding conventions. Bilingual signage in this sector serves both a practical and symbolic role: it ensures accessibility while signaling the hotel's alignment with international standards. Pharmacies, on the other hand, lead in multilingual signage. Their signs often feature three or more languages, especially Thai, English, Chinese, Russian, and Korean. Interviews with pharmacy staff confirmed that these multilingual strategies are driven by the need for clear, accurate communication about healthcare services and medications. In a tourist hub like Pattaya, multilingual signage in pharmacies is essential for supporting health access and minimizing miscommunication.

This variation in signage types across sectors shows how language use is calibrated to the communicative function and audience expectations of each business. Monolingual signs are efficient and direct, ideal for casual or high-turnover venues. Bilingual signs reflect inclusivity and professionalism, especially in regulated sectors like hospitality. Multilingual signs serve highly practical purposes where misunderstanding could have serious consequences, as in healthcare and pharmacies.

Overall, language use in signage is driven by sector-specific needs, customer targeting, and perceived economic benefits. Thai remains a legal and cultural anchor, while English serves as the default for international communication (cf. Sari et al., 2024). Other languages are incorporated based on demographic proximity and tourist flows. This selective use of language illustrates the principle of language commodification (Heller, 2010), where linguistic features are mobilized to attract customers, enhance trust, and signal market alignment.

Signage across Pattaya's commercial landscape functions not merely as a medium of communication, but as a semiotic and economic tool. Language selection and presentation are shaped by a complex interplay of local regulation, global influence, and business pragmatism. This multilingualism, while unevenly distributed, reflects the city's deep integration into global tourism economies. These patterns of language use provide a foundation for the next section, which examines how languages are visually ordered, sized, and spatially arranged to create linguistic hierarchies and convey symbolic meaning within signs.

4.2. Linguistic hierarchy, visibility, and layout

Based on the analysis presented in section 4.1, the findings led to further examination in this section, which focuses on the languages displayed on signs; there is also an examination of the synthesis results, including the use of varying font sizes on signs for different types of businesses. This can indicate the perspective on the importance of languages embedded in the awareness of the business operators. It aims to communicate with language user groups

within the local community, reflecting which languages are spoken or used most frequently. Moreover, the order of languages displayed on signage clearly indicates that business owners are able to prioritize or identify customer groups that frequently use their services and visit Pattaya. This observation aligns with statistical data on both returning and new tourist arrivals, as presented in Appendices A and B.

Based on Appendix B, language hierarchy on signs reflects efforts to expand customer reach and accommodate Pattaya's diverse tourist population. Signage typically appears in monolingual, bilingual, or multilingual formats. When three or more languages are used, they often correspond to major tourist groups—such as Chinese, Russian, Japanese, Hindi, Korean, and Vietnamese speakers. Monolingual signs frequently feature Thai, while alternative single-language signs, including English, Chinese, Korean, and German, are used depending on business clientele. Bilingual signs commonly pair Thai with English, or English with languages such as Russian, Chinese, Korean, German, or Hindi. The presence of these language combinations across different signs highlights the linguistic diversity of tourists visiting Pattaya's various areas.

On the other hand, the sequence of languages and the size of fonts used on signs are key factors that prompt business operators to acknowledge the importance of language and the presence of diverse linguistic communities in Pattaya. In addition, legal and tax considerations play a significant role in influencing language choices for signage. Based on informal interviews with business operators, four main factors can be identified in the decision-making process regarding signage language: (1) target customer groups, (2) tax signage regulations, (3) formal and international standards, and (4) community in residential areas.

Target Customer Groups: Signage is explicitly designed to reflect the intended audience. Businesses targeting Thai clients often use only Thai, while those focusing on foreign tourists include English or other languages. Large, bold English targets foreign tourists at a distance, while smaller Thai text fulfills regulatory roles and speaks to local passersby already familiar with the context. In some cases, Thai is used only for certain terms (e.g., product names or 'welcome' greetings), reinforcing its limited communicative role in the visual hierarchy. In vertical stacked signage (See figure 3 Below) commonly used in massage shops and pharmacies, English is placed at eye level, while Thai and additional languages such as Chinese or Korean appear in descending order. This pattern is especially evident in signs using lightboxes or plastic panels, where line placement mirrors assumed customer priorities.

Tax Signage Regulations: Language use is also shaped by municipal signage tax policy. Interviews with business owners revealed that including Thai in signage qualifies businesses for reduced tax rates. This incentivizes the

inclusion of Thai at least nominally, even if it is visually marginalized. Some business owners strategically place Thai at the top or include it alongside English for cost reasons. As noted by Backhaus (2006) in his study of Japanese train signage, English also functions as a symbol of modernity and internationalism. This is evident in accommodation signs where English is often bold and dominant, while Thai is smaller and serves regulatory or symbolic roles (See figure 2).

Figure 2.

An Example of an Accommodation Sign (Source: Sarot, 2022)

Formal and International Standards: Language layout often reflects adherence to formal or industry-specific norms, especially in the accommodation sector. International hotels frequently display Thai and English, with English in larger fonts or higher positions, aligning with global branding and hospitality practices. In contrast, smaller or local accommodations—like apartments—often use monolingual signage, depending on whether their clientele is Thai or foreign. Font size and language selection are also shaped by ownership structures, especially in foreign-owned or joint ventures, which often favor English prominently.

Community in Residential Areas: Signage in residential streets varies in complexity based on community identity and tourism exposure. According to Schiffman (1996, as cited in Huebner, 2006), the linguistic landscape reflects the social and cultural features of urban communities. In Pattaya, some areas show homogeneous patterns across connected streets due to similar tourist traffic and infrastructure. However, certain areas undergoing rapid transformation—such as those near international hospitals or nightlife zones—exhibit marked shifts in signage. Figure 3 (below), for example, reflects how pharmacy signage has evolved to accommodate a multilingual clientele, changing font sizes and layout to accommodate functional multilingualism.

According to the visual analysis, Figure 3 demonstrates a sign where several languages—i.e., Thai, English, Russian, Korean, and Chinese—are rendered in large, legible fonts. Thai appears first, followed by English, with the remaining foreign languages presented in no clear hierarchical order. This arrangement reflects the business owner's intent to communicate with a linguistically diverse clientele while still giving symbolic and communicative precedence to Thai and English. Although the position of these languages varies, the relatively uniform font sizes indicate a desire to ensure readability and inclusive access to information for tourists from multiple nationalities.

Figure 3.
Multilingual Pharmacy Sign (Source: Sarot, 2022)

Figure 4.
Foreign Languages Displayed on Mirrors and Supplementary Shopfront Signs (Source: Sarot, 2022)

Thai, English, Chinese

English, Chinese, Korean

Beyond the main signage structure, many businesses also employ supplementary signage or additional language displays to provide more detailed service information. These are typically applied as glass-door stickers, window decals, or semi-permanent placards placed near entrances. While not part of the primary storefront signage, these additions are intentionally designed to enhance language coverage and target specific tourist groups. As illustrated in Figure 4 (above), one example includes adhesive signs in Chinese and

Korean—languages not prominently featured on the main sign—affixed to the storefront glass. These supplementary texts often provide descriptions of services such as massage types, operating hours, or pricing. Business owners select these additional languages based on observed patterns of service use, particularly among nationalities that frequently patronize their establishments.

This strategy aligns with tourism data indicating a strong presence of Chinese and Korean tourists in Thailand, especially in Pattaya. Interviews confirm that many of these visitors actively seek out services such as traditional Thai massage. As such, business owners adapt by integrating these languages into peripheral signage to accommodate shifting tourist demographics and expand market reach. The result is a dynamic and flexible signage system, combining fixed and semi-fixed visual communication tools tailored to the evolving needs of international clientele.

Figure 5.

Multilingual Sign of a Government Agency (Source: Sarot, 2022)

Five Languages appearing on Government Organization Sign: Thai /English/ Russian/ Chinese/ Arabic

The arrangement of languages on signage, including language order and font size, reflects both legal requirements and business strategies. Signage tax regulations encourage the inclusion of Thai, while the use of prominent foreign languages, especially English, addresses the need to communicate with a diverse tourist base. These factors together have shaped Pattaya's multilingual landscape, particularly in high-tourism areas. The growing presence of multiple languages has also raised awareness among local authorities, leading

to efforts to enhance multilingual accessibility in public services. A key example is the multilingual sign by Pattaya City Police Station, shown in Figure 5 (above), which provides essential information in several languages to support communication and public safety for both locals and tourists—highlighting the city's recognition of its evolving linguistic diversity.

The languages displayed on the government-issued sign in Figure 6 reflect a growing effort by local authorities to communicate effectively with international visitors and provide critical public services. This multilingual signage, produced by the Pattaya City Police Station, was designed to offer guidance on safety, assistance procedures, and access to multilingual volunteers who serve as interpreters when tourists encounter difficulties. Interviews with officials confirm that such initiatives are part of a broader effort to foster public understanding and acceptance of multilingualism, underpinned by municipal policies that explicitly promote linguistic inclusion.

This shift aligns with Kallen and Dhonnacha's (2010) observation that multilingualism and globalization are increasingly integrated into urban societies, where languages beyond the national official language play key roles in public communication (cf. Salmani Nodoushan, 2021). Historically, the use of foreign languages in public signage was limited. However, with the spread of globalization, Pattaya has undergone a transition toward becoming a multilingual urban society, where language use is shaped by economic, social, and cultural factors. The presence of multiple languages on signage represents a clear embrace of borderless communication and the recognition of language as a tool for facilitating tourism and cross-cultural interaction.

Interviews also revealed that government stakeholders are aware of the importance of multilingualism in supporting Pattaya's economic development. As the city positions itself as a major tourist hub in the Eastern region, the coexistence of long-term residents, entrepreneurs, and international tourists has intensified language exchange. Business transactions and service encounters frequently involve code-switching, translation, or simplified multilingual interactions, reinforcing the practical necessity of linguistic diversity for service delivery and hospitality.

The growing presence of multilingual signage has also influenced local government planning. Agencies have begun to integrate language considerations into urban development frameworks, particularly through capacity-building measures aimed at improving communication with international tourists. One prominent example is the "NEO PATTAYA" strategic development initiative, as mentioned in interviews with Pattaya City Municipality officials. This project includes language training for government staff, the production of multilingual public relations materials, and efforts to align Pattaya's tourism infrastructure with international service standards. The overarching goal is to enhance the

city's global reputation while improving public sector readiness for tourist engagement.

Although the public sector's multilingual signage efforts remain less extensive than those of the private sector, this initiative marks a significant institutional shift. It demonstrates an emerging awareness of linguistic diversity as a component of inclusive city planning. Moreover, the "NEO PATTAYA" plan supports tourism indirectly through improvements in urban infrastructure, visual aesthetics, and service access, positioning the city for continued growth as a multilingual destination. This governmental momentum represents a critical foundation for the future expansion of multilingual practices in public spaces, aligning Pattaya's urban development with its increasingly global tourist profile.

4.3. Top-down vs. bottom-up signage practices

This section explores the contrast between top-down and bottom-up signage in Pattaya, highlighting differences in language use, visual design, communicative goals, and regulatory influence. Drawing on the framework established by Ben-Rafael et al. (2006), top-down signage refers to signs created by government agencies or public institutions, while bottom-up signage originates from private business owners, individuals, or local community actors.

Top-down signs in Pattaya are mainly produced by government institutions such as city offices, police stations, and hospitals. These signs typically follow standardized formats and are influenced by regulations and 'symbolic functions' (cf. Salmani Nodoushan, 2022, 2025 on 'meaning' and 'function'). Most prioritize Thai as the official language, with English added to accommodate basic tourist communication. As shown in Figure 5, the Pattaya City Police Station is one of the few examples of multilingual public signage, using Thai, English, and other languages to enhance accessibility and public safety. However, such cases are rare. Most government signs remain bilingual at most, with minimal attention to font hierarchy, visibility, or audience-specific design.

Interviews with municipal officials revealed growing awareness of the city's multilingual demands, yet also acknowledged constraints such as budget limitations, policy inertia, and a lack of multilingual training among public staff. Projects like NEO PATTAYA represent early efforts to shift this trend by incorporating multilingualism into public-facing communication and service planning. Still, the top-down approach remains cautious and formal, with signage typically serving administrative and informational functions rather than competitive marketing.

In contrast, bottom-up signage created by private business owners is marked by flexibility, creativity, and responsiveness to tourism trends. These signs show diverse language use, font styles, and layouts. Businesses choose languages based on target customers, tourist patterns, and market competition. As shown in Figures 2 to 4, private signs often include multiple foreign languages such as English, Chinese, Russian, Korean, and Arabic. English is typically the primary language, while others appear alongside or below it depending on the business strategy. Thai is included mainly to meet signage tax regulations but is often smaller or placed less prominently. Business owners also add language elements like glass stickers, sidewalk signs, or product labels—especially in spas, pharmacies, and restaurants. These semi-permanent additions allow businesses to reach wider audiences without changing the main signage. This form of multilingualism arises not from government policy, but from direct customer interaction and economic adaptation.

The contrast between top-down and bottom-up signage in Pattaya reflects deeper differences in (1) ‘purpose’, (2) ‘agency’, and (3) ‘linguistic ideology’ (cf. Salmani Nodoushan, 2020, 2022, 2025 for more on these topics). Top-down signs aim for public order, regulation, and formal communication, prioritizing Thai and using ‘English for basic tourist accommodation’—which is a form of English for Occupational Purposes (EOP) (cf. Salmani Nodoushan, 2020). While, bottom-up signs are commercial tools, designed to attract attention, segment customers, and convey branding. They reflect language commodification and multilingual pragmatism. Moreover, while government signs tend to lag behind social realities, private signage often leads in reflecting real-time demographic and cultural changes such as shifts in dominant tourist groups or the emergence of new consumer behaviors.

The dual forces of institutional regulation and entrepreneurial adaptation shape Pattaya’s linguistic landscape in complementary but contrasting ways. Top-down signage remains formal, Thai-dominant, and cautious in its multilingual engagement. In contrast, bottom-up signage is dynamic, customer-focused, and multilingual in both content and design. Understanding this divide is essential for interpreting Pattaya’s urban identity and for planning future efforts to promote inclusive and functional multilingual communication across both public and private sectors.

4.4. Geographic patterns and linguistic stratification in Pattaya

This section argues how multilingual signage varies across different zones of Pattaya, revealing geographic patterns of linguistic density, visibility, and inequality. The spatial distribution of signage is closely tied to tourist demographics, business strategies, and socio-economic zoning, with central

areas displaying dense multilingual layering and peripheral zones remaining largely monolingual. This unevenness suggests the presence of linguistic stratification—a spatial hierarchy in language visibility driven by market logic, tourism clustering, and symbolic inclusion or exclusion:

- North Pattaya: Transitional multilingualism and regulated layouts;
- Central Pattaya: High-density linguistic saturation and commercial visibility; and
- South Pattaya: Ethnolinguistic clustering and long-stay influence

North Pattaya features a moderate concentration of multilingual signage, particularly near mixed-use areas that combine mid-tier accommodations, shopping arcades, and local eateries. Most signage here is bilingual (Thai-English) or includes a third language (e.g., Chinese or Russian) in smaller fonts. English maintains visual prominence, often appearing at the top or in bold, while Thai typically follows in smaller font or secondary placement.

Signage design in this zone tends to be uniform and regulatory-compliant, using standardized fonts and durable materials (e.g., printed boards, lightboxes). This reflects the dual presence of local governance offices and medium-scale private businesses that must balance tourism engagement with regulatory adherence. Signs are often designed to last, with minimal layering of temporary or ad hoc language elements, suggesting a less aggressive but stable multilingual communication strategy. Businesses here appear to serve a mixed clientele—domestic tourists, local families, and budget international travelers—resulting in signs that are inclusive but not highly segmented. The visual tone is pragmatic rather than promotional, with multilingualism used functionally but without the stylistic competitiveness seen in more tourist-saturated zones. One of the main routes in this area, Naklua Street, connects to central Pattaya and is lined with businesses run by long-established residents. Here, signage is overwhelmingly Thai, especially in early street segments, reinforcing the area's local orientation. Foreign language use is largely absent in these settings, and when it appears, it is often limited to basic English terms for recognition rather than full communication.

In summary, North Pattaya presents a transitional multilingual zone, with strong monolingual Thai foundations and selective bilingual development in tourist-access corridors. Multilingual signage remains concentrated in institutional settings, and its presence reflects a cautious, purpose-driven expansion rather than a widespread multilingual shift. The area's signage practices highlight the layered nature of Pattaya's linguistic landscape, where language visibility is shaped by local demographics, institutional presence, and selective tourist engagement.

By way of contrast, Central Pattaya, particularly along Walking Street and the beachfront corridor, represents the most linguistically saturated zone in the city. This area exhibits the highest density of signage and the most complex multilingual arrangements, often displaying four to five languages, including English, Thai, Chinese, Russian, Arabic, and Korean. The visual environment is intensely competitive; signage is designed with large fonts, vibrant colors, animated light displays, and layered promotional banners that create a dynamic and highly saturated 'semiotic' landscape—for more on 'semiotics', see Salmani Nodoushan (2016, 2018, 2021, 2025).

In this context, language functions as a branding tool. English dominates in placement and typography, often appearing in bold, stylized fonts at the top of signs. Chinese and Russian typically occupy secondary positions in mid-sized fonts, while Arabic or Korean appear in smaller sizes or on additional signage. These patterns reflect strategic prioritization based on tourist demographics and shifting visitor trends. Business owners frequently update their signs to stay culturally relevant and competitive, adjusting language order and content to align with seasonal tourist flows. This creates a functional linguistic hierarchy: English projects internationalism and broad accessibility; Chinese and Russian target key tourist groups; and Thai, though legally required, is often minimized in size or placement. Multilingualism here is not just for communication but serves as a commercial strategy, positioning signage as a dynamic link between local businesses and global tourism.

Interviews with shop owners reinforce this analysis. Respondents described their language selection as deliberate and data-driven, often informed by customer feedback, partnerships with international tour operators, and changes in tourist nationality across high and low seasons. The widespread use of temporary signage—such as plastic banners, vinyl decals, and window stickers—further demonstrates a high degree of linguistic adaptability, unique to this high-density commercial zone.

Despite this visual complexity, observational analysis reveals that monolingual and bilingual signs still outnumber multilingual ones. This aligns with the findings of Prasert and Zilli (2019), who observed that even in globally oriented tourism districts like Walking Street, multilingual signage remains less prevalent than expected, with most signs appearing in either English alone or in Thai-English combinations. This may be due to space limitations, stylistic preferences, or economic considerations, including signage taxation policies that influence language choice and layout.

Many signs in this area use English exclusively, particularly for 'agogo' bars and clubs. These signs prioritize simplicity and clarity, using globally recognized terms like "A GOGO" to convey the venue's style and purpose. Thai may appear in small fonts, usually in a corner, to meet signage tax regulations that reduce

fees when Thai is included. As illustrated in Figure 6, agogo venues vary their signage through font, color, and lighting while keeping consistent English phrasing. These design choices reflect branding strategies aimed at efficiently attracting English-speaking visitors without relying on multilingual explanations.

Figure 6.

Bar and Nightclub Signs (Source: Sarot, 2022)

In summary, Central Pattaya exemplifies a high-intensity linguistic economy, where signage is multilayered, commercialized, and visually competitive. English dominates as both a communicative and symbolic language, while other foreign languages are selectively employed based on tourist segmentation. Thai is often relegated to a secondary or peripheral role, used strategically to comply with tax regulations. While true multilingual signs are visible, they remain outnumbered by more targeted bilingual or monolingual formats. This area thus illustrates how language in signage operates as a flexible tool of tourism commerce, shaped by both global mobility and local regulation.

In South Pattaya, including Jomtien Beach and nearby streets, signage reveals distinct ethnolinguistic clustering based on dominant tourist and expatriate groups. Streets in this zone often display signage in Russian–English or Chinese–English, depending on the local customer base. This pattern reflects a niche approach to multilingualism, driven by long-stay visitors and community-specific commercial networks. Many businesses specialize in services tailored to repeat or culturally aligned visitors—halal restaurants display Arabic, massage parlors use Chinese or Korean, and minimarts operated by foreigners often use only Russian. Signage in these spaces is typically custom-made and informal, including hand-painted boards, vinyl stickers, or banner-style signs. Thai is frequently absent, especially in enclaves with high concentrations of expatriates. This absence is not accidental, but rather a market strategy aimed at specific ethnic communities.

These signage choices create semi-closed linguistic environments, where languages function as markers of group identity and familiarity. In these micro-communities, language selection supports both commercial targeting and social cohesion, reducing the need for linguistic inclusivity outside the

intended demographic. A key example is Pattaya Second Street (Pattaya Sai Song), which connects to South Pattaya Road. This area features a mix of monolingual, bilingual, and multilingual signs, reflecting its diverse business landscape and community composition. Here, Arab and Indian businesses—including restaurants, jewelry shops, and spice markets—use signage in Arabic, Hindi, and English. While the visual focus is on cultural alignment, many establishments still welcome customers from different backgrounds, especially those familiar with or interested in Middle Eastern and South Asian cuisine.

This variation in signage aligns with broader patterns in Appendices A and B, showing that language choices are closely linked to business type and tourist nationality. In this context, signage serves both practical and symbolic functions, reflecting community identity. The use of Arabic, Cyrillic, or Devanagari scripts highlights cultural inclusion and signals hospitality toward specific long-stay groups. Multilingualism in South Pattaya is shaped not only by business decisions but also by tourism-driven municipal initiatives. Interviews with government officials indicate that events such as international fireworks festivals, water sports competitions, and cultural fairs attract tourists from targeted regions, increasing the need for multilingual signage. Although there is no explicit language policy, these efforts indirectly support multilingual communication in key service sectors.

In sum, South Pattaya reflects a localized and identity-oriented model of multilingualism. Signage serves both commercial and symbolic roles—helping businesses reach their primary audience while reinforcing cultural familiarity. Unlike Central Pattaya’s broad-spectrum multilingualism, South Pattaya’s language landscape is segmented and community-specific, shaped by patterns of long-term residence, repeat tourism, and cultural clustering.

5. Discussion

This study’s analysis of multilingual signage in Pattaya reveals the critical role of language in shaping urban communication and reflecting cultural dynamics within a tourism-dependent city. While Thai remains the foundational language, widely used in local communities and on public signage, the emergence and visibility of foreign languages—particularly English, Chinese, Russian, Korean, and Arabic—illustrate Pattaya’s evolution into a multilingual urban society.

Across all sign types and business sectors, the primary purpose of signage is to facilitate communication with target audiences by providing essential information about products and services. Signage is therefore crafted to be concise, accessible, and understandable. Business operators consistently emphasized the importance of linguistic clarity and appropriateness for their clientele, reflecting a shared recognition of language as a functional and strategic tool for communication (cf. Sari et al., 2024).

In Pattaya, there is a widespread understanding that Thai serves as the official and cultural baseline, with strong historical, national, and regulatory significance. It functions not only as the default language for locals but also as a formal requirement for signage taxation. In contrast, English is positioned as the most influential foreign language, serving as a global 'lingua franca' (cf. Salmani Nodoushan, 2024) across education, commerce, and international tourism. Additional languages—such as Chinese, Russian, Arabic, and Korean—have gained importance in response to shifting tourist demographics and economic partnerships, and are increasingly integrated into signage to engage specific visitor groups.

The findings demonstrate that multilingual signage is not evenly distributed but appears in spatially patterned ways. Commercial districts, tourist corridors, and zones with high foreign residency show greater linguistic diversity, while peripheral areas remain largely monolingual. Pattaya's signage landscape reflects what Huebner (2006) described in Bangkok as 'linguistic islands', where multilingualism develops in response to neighborhood-specific needs. However, Pattaya is unique in the breadth of its multilingual presence—across private businesses and limited but notable public signage—often featuring three to five languages in a single location. These signs serve a dual function: they are tools of pragmatic communication and also symbols of openness and cosmopolitanism. The integration of foreign languages into signage supports cultural recognition and promotes a sense of inclusivity among international visitors. In this way, multilingual signage is not merely a response to economic demands but also an expression of sociocultural adaptation to globalization.

Pattaya's signage practices also challenge the traditional linguistic landscape dichotomy between top-down and bottom-up signage. While government signs remain largely monolingual or bilingual, many private businesses have developed complex, multilingual signage systems that are more responsive, creative, and socially embedded. These bottom-up practices do not simply resist or complement state regulations—they effectively fill the gaps of public policy by localizing multilingual communication. This suggests that Pattaya may serve as a model for decentralized multilingual city-making, where language planning emerges organically through grassroots entrepreneurship and dynamic tourist interactions, rather than being centrally imposed.

To support this bottom-up momentum and promote equity in language access, policy recommendations should be considered. Municipal authorities could develop clear multilingual signage guidelines that encourage visual balance, font accessibility, and inclusive language selection across all business sectors. Urban planners and designers should integrate linguistic diversity into spatial planning, ensuring that wayfinding systems, public signs, and urban branding

materials reflect the city's multilingual character. At the same time, local business associations could offer language support resources or collaborative signage initiatives for small enterprises that may lack the means to implement multilingual communication independently.

6. Conclusion

In conclusion, Pattaya represents a dynamic example of a multilingual urban society in transition. Signage serves as both a mirror of and a mechanism for this transformation, capturing the city's cultural plurality, economic orientation, and evolving urban identity. Through the collaborative efforts of government agencies, business owners, and community members, multilingual signage has become embedded in the city's visual landscape, contributing to Pattaya's position as an internationally accessible and culturally diverse destination. The case of Pattaya provides valuable insights for other cities navigating the intersection of globalization, tourism, and inclusive urban design.

Authors' Statement

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Appendix A: Languages displayed on monolingual, bilingual, and multilingual signs for each business type

business Type	Sign Type		
	Monolingual	Bilingual	Multilingual
Pharmacy	Thai English	Thai-English	Thai-English-Chinese Thai-English-Russian Thai-English-Chinese-Russian Thai-English-Russian-Chinese Thai-Chinese-English-German Thai-English-Russian-Korean-Chinese Thai-English-German-Chinese-Russian
Healthcare	Thai English	Thai-English Thai-Chinese	Thai-English-Arabic
Money Exchange	English	Thai-English	Thai-English-Russian Thai-English-Chinese Thai-English-Russian-Chinese Thai-English-Chinese-Russian Thai-English-Hindi-Chinese
Thai Massage and Spa	English Thai	Thai-English English-Korean	Thai-Chinese-English Thai-English-Russian Thai-English-Chinese-Korean-Japanese
Accommodation	English	Thai-English	Thai-English-Chinese
Pub, Bar and Restaurant	Thai English German Korean	Thai-Chinese Thai-German Thai-English English-Hindi Chinese-English Korean-Chinese	Thai-Vietnamese-English Thai-English-Chinese Thai-Hindi-Russian Thai-English-Korean Thai-English-Arabic Thai-English-Hindi Thai-English-Japanese Thai-English-Hindi-Russian Hindi-English-Thai-Arabic Thai-English-Hindi-Chinese-Russian Thai-English-Russian-Chinese-Arabic
Other businesses	Thai English Chinese	Thai-English Russian-English	Thai-Japanese-English Thai-English-Russian Thai-Chinese-English

Appendix B: Languages Mainly Displayed on Signs

All Types of Signs	Most Prominent Language	Optional Language	Followed by
Monolingual	Thai	English Chinese Korean German	-
Bilingual	Thai-English	-	Russian/Chinese/Korean/ German/Hindi
Multilingual (Three languages)	Thai-English	-	Russian/Chinese/Hindi/Arabic/ Korean/Japanese/Vietnamese
Multilingual (Four languages)	Thai-English	-	Russian/Chinese/Hindi/Arabic/ Korean/German
Multilingual (Five languages)	Thai-English	-	Russian/Chinese/Hindi/Korean/ Japanese/German